

Electron-electron-ion triple-coincidence experiment of electron-initiated valence ionization of small water clusters

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The ionization and fragmentation of small water clusters induced by electron impact (80 eV) is investigated. Using a multiparticle coincidence spectrometer (reaction microscope), all three charged final state particles—two outgoing electrons and one fragment ion—are detected. Nonprotonated $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ and protonated water clusters H_3O^+ , $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{H}^+$, $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_4\text{H}^+$, and $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{H}^+$ are identified in the measured ion spectrum. The ionization channels for formation of these species are investigated by measuring the kinetic energy distributions and the electronic states of the ions. Only a single state can lead to $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$, which is identified as ionization of water dimer with a $1b_1$ hole at the hydrogen bonding donor molecule, while for the protonated water species three major electronic states corresponding to the ionization of $1b_1$, $3a_1$, and $1b_2$ type orbitals are observed.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Water is ubiquitous on Earth and plays a significant role in numerous scientific and technological applications. The understanding of electron-initiated processes in aqueous systems is of great importance because they can efficiently form highly reactive radicals, notably hydroxyl radical (OH) and protonated species, which are relevant in a variety of fields, such as radiation chemistry, reactive plasmas, nuclear reactor technologies, planetary atmospheres, and environmental sciences [1–3]. For example, in medical radiation therapy an important part of DNA damage is produced by low-energy secondary electrons (<100 eV) through various nonresonant excitation, ionization, and dissociation processes and through resonant dissociative electron attachment processes [3,4]. These electrons are produced in large quantities by high-energy ionizing radiation ($\sim 5 \times 10^4$ electrons by a 1-MeV deposited energy) and lead to clustered damages in biomolecules due to their short range and high-interaction cross sections [5].

Water clusters are important hydrogen-bonded complexes because of their unique role in both fundamental research and a wide range of applied fields. There has been intense research on the electronic structure and the fragmentation dynamics of water clusters and liquid water using photoion-

ization accompanied by electron spectroscopy [6–11] and by time-of-flight (TOF) mass spectroscopy [12–18]. These results showed that the mass spectra of cluster ions are dominated by the protonated species, which originate from a fast proton transfer process from the ionized molecule followed by internal rearrangement of the cluster. Thus, the ionized cluster is vibrationally excited, resulting in the emission of OH and water molecules. Interestingly, if the water clusters are embedded in argon clusters, nonprotonated water cluster ions are observed with a higher intensity than the protonated cluster ions [19,20]. Here, the internal vibrational energy can be dissipated by evaporating Ar atoms cooling down the cluster ion and stabilizing it. The appearance energy for ions significantly decreases going from H_2O to $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$, followed by a gradual decrease for increasing cluster size up to $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{23}$ [17]. This shows the behavior of the first ionization potential in going from single molecules to the bulk. Recent photoionization experiments have investigated inner-valence ionization of water dimers [21], larger water clusters [22], and liquid water [23], and have found that the system decays via the intermolecular Coulombic decay (ICD) process and releases a low-energy electron and a pair of energetic ions [24,25]. Compared to the abundant studies of water clusters using photon absorption, electron-collision-induced ionization of water clusters has, so far, rarely been studied. Existing experiments mostly used TOF mass spectroscopy to investigate the yields of different fragmentation channels and their appearance energies [26–28].

In the present work, ionization and fragmentation of water clusters is studied using an electron-electron-ion triple-coincidence or $(e, 2e + \text{ion})$ technique [29–33]. Small water clusters $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ with $n < 10$, generated in a supersonic gas expansion, are ionized by projectile electrons with an energy of $E_0 = 80$ eV. This energy is close to the mean energy of

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secondary electrons produced along the tracks of high-energy primary radiation traversing media [5]. We measured the kinetic energies of two final-state electrons (E_1 and E_2) together with one resulting cluster cation. These are the nonprotonated water dimer ion ($(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$), the hydronium ion (H_3O^+), the Zundel-type ion ($(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{H}^+$), the Eigen-type ion ($(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4\text{H}^+$), and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{H}^+$. The kinetic energy distribution for a specific cluster ion and the corresponding electron binding energy ($\text{BE} = E_0 - E_1 - E_2$) spectrum are obtained and compared to the results from the ionization of water monomer (H_2O). These data show that the observed ions are produced initially from larger clusters which dissociate and evaporate neutral water molecules. Thus, insight on the formation mechanisms of various radical ions in aqueous solution is provided.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Experiments were performed using a multiparticle coincidence momentum spectrometer (reaction microscope) specially built for electron-impact ionization studies. Details of the setup were described elsewhere [29,34,35]. A brief outline will be given here. A well-focused (≈ 1 mm diameter), pulsed electron beam with an energy of $E_0 = 80$ eV was crossed with a continuous supersonic gas jet. The pulsed electron beam is produced by an electron gun, in which a pulsed ultraviolet laser beam ($\lambda = 266$ nm, $\Delta t < 0.5$ ns) illuminates a tantalum photocathode [29]. The energy and temporal width of the electron pulses are about 0.5 eV (ΔE_0) and 0.5 ns (ΔT_0), respectively. Water clusters are formed in a supersonic gas expansion of 1 bar helium with seeded water vapor (liquid water maintained at 80°C , giving rise to about 400 mbar vapor pressure) through a $30\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ nozzle orifice. The gas beam is collimated by two skimmers with $200\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ -diameter aperture at their apex, and located approximately 0.4 and 2 cm downstream from the nozzle. Under these conditions, small-size water clusters are expected to be produced. This is indicated by our cluster ion TOF data, where we could not identify cluster sizes beyond $n = 10$. For comparison, Adoui *et al.* [36] used similar jet parameters for water cluster production except for using argon as the carrying gas, and they observed clusters ions up to $n \approx 20$.

Experimental data were obtained using the triple-coincidence detection of two outgoing electrons (e_1 and e_2) and one fragment ion. Homogeneous electric and magnetic fields are used to guide electrons and ions into opposite directions onto two respective position- and time-sensitive detectors. By measuring the times-of-flight and the impact positions for all particles, their vector momenta are determined. The projectile beam axis (defining the longitudinal direction) is adjusted parallel to the electric and magnetic extraction fields. Therefore, the electron gun is placed in front of the ion detector and after passing the target gas jet, the electron beam arrives at the center of the electron detector, where a central bore in the detector allows for the nonscattered electrons to pass without inducing detector signals. The acceptance angle for detection of electrons up to the energy of 15 eV is close to 4π , apart from the acceptance holes at small forward and backward angles where the electrons end up in the detector bore. In fragmentation processes, the dissociated ions are often created with a relatively high kinetic

FIG. 1. Fragment ion TOF spectrum of small water clusters produced by electron-impact ionization. Shaded area represents TOF region without experimental detection. The inset shows the ion signal intensity for the indicated TOF window vs TOF and position with respect to the center of the ion image.

energy (compared to the intact species) and require higher extraction fields than the electrons. Therefore, 400 ns after the collision when the electrons have reached the detector, the electric extraction field is ramped up from 1 to 20 V/cm for extraction of the fragment ions [29,30]. In this way, the ions from the present ionization and dissociation processes are collected over the full 4π solid angle. It is also to be noted that before hitting the microchannel plate of the detector the ions are accelerated to about 2200 eV in order to reach reasonable detection efficiencies. These range from 48% for the lightest ions (H_2O^+ , H_3O^+) to 32% for the heaviest ions considered $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{H}^+$ [37]. The data are corrected for these efficiencies where relevant.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The properties of liquid water are determined by the complex network of intermolecular hydrogen bonds. By studying water clusters of increasing size one can get insight into how these properties emerge. The valence shell electronic configuration of the water monomer (C_{2v} geometry) is given as $(2a_1)^2(1b_2)^2(3a_1)^2(1b_1)^2$. Ionization resulting in vacancies $(1b_1)^{-1}$, $(3a_1)^{-1}$, $(1b_2)^{-1}$, or $(2a_1)^{-1}$ corresponds to the electronic states $\tilde{X}^2\text{B}_1$, $\tilde{A}^2\text{A}_1$, $\tilde{B}^2\text{B}_2$, or $\tilde{C}^2\text{A}_1$ with binding energies of 12.6, 14.8, 18.7, and 32.4 eV, respectively.

Earlier studies have analyzed the fragmentation pathways for ionization of H_2O in the above listed four outer orbitals [38]. Ionization of the upper two orbitals $1b_1$ and $3a_1$ yields stable H_2O^+ ions while removal of an electron from the $1b_2$ orbital most likely results in emission of H (OH^+ channel, 70%) or H^+ (22%) and with a minor contribution to H_2O^+ (8%). The inner valence ionization in the $2a_1$ orbital most likely produces H^+ but also O^+ (26%) [38].

The measured ion TOF spectrum for electron-impact ionization of water monomers and small water clusters is presented in Fig. 1. The reaction products of the water monomers in the TOF range shown are H_2O^+ , OH^+ , and O^+ . Furthermore, H^+ at smaller TOF is found (not shown). The ions with larger masses beyond H_2O^+ originate from

FIG. 2. Kinetic energy distributions for H_2O^+ and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$. The spectra are normalized to unity at the peak maximum.

ionization of clusters. It is seen that the protonated water clusters (H_3O^+ , $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{H}^+$, $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_4\text{H}^+$, $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{H}^+$) are by far the major species obtained in the ionization process of clusters. The $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_3\text{H}^+$ cation is missing due to a TOF dead-time window in the respective TOF region, which is set up to block the noise present on the detector signal cables during ramping of the pulsed electric extraction field. The only nonprotonated cluster ion observed is $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$, for which it is known that the ion structure is $\text{H}_3\text{O}^+\text{OH}$, i.e., there is proton transfer but no dissociation [39]. These ions can be more clearly seen from the inset of Fig. 1, which shows the ion signal intensity as a function of TOF and position on the detector with respect to the center of the ion image. The narrow widths of the $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ peak in both directions corresponds to a small momentum spread of these ions and indicates that there is no recoil and, therefore, no dissociation process involved. In contrast, the nearby lying $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{H}^+$ ions resulting from emission of OH and possibly neutral water molecules show significant larger spread in TOF and position. The kinetic energy (KE) distributions for H_2O^+ and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ are presented in Fig. 2. The averaged KEs are very small and amount to 4.5 meV for H_2O^+ and 6.5 meV for $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$. These values are much smaller than what is regularly seen for dissociation, e.g., for the protonated species (see below). On the other hand, the momentum transfer from the projectile in the ionizing collision leads to estimated recoil energies which are even smaller than 1 meV. Therefore, the observed KEs reflect the experimental KE resolution for the ions, which is due to the finite temperature of the target gas and to the finite resolution of the spectrometer. From the mean KE of 4.5 meV one obtains an upper limit of 35 K target temperature, which is a reasonable value. Therefore, the low KE for H_2O^+ and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ demonstrates that these ions stem from the parent monomers and dimers, respectively, and not from dissociation of larger clusters.

More information on the ionization channels leading to specific cluster ions is obtained from the coincident measurement of the ion kinetic energy distribution and the BE ($E_0 - E_1 - E_2$) spectrum. The BE observed in our experiment represents the vertical Franck-Condon transition energy from the neutral initial state to the ionic final state. Here, the energy scale of the spectra is calibrated with a BE measurement of the

FIG. 3. (a) BE spectrum for ionization of water monomers resulting in stable H_2O^+ ions. (b) BE spectrum for water dimers resulting in stable $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ ions. The open circles and open squares are the experimental data. The dashed lines are fitted Gaussian peaks corresponding to ionization of particular orbitals and the solid lines are the sum of the fits. The spectra are normalized to unity at the peak maximum and they are offset vertically for better visibility. The insets in (a) and (b) represent the minimum energy structures of the water monomer and dimer, respectively.

Ar(3p) orbital. A BE resolution of $\Delta E = 2.5$ eV (FWHM) has been obtained in the present experiment.

Figures 3(a) and 3(b) present the BE spectra obtained for the nonprotonated water ions H_2O^+ and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$, respectively. The measured BE spectra are analyzed with a Gaussian fitting procedure, where the widths and the positions of the lines are fitting parameters. The line widths are determined by the experimental resolution and the Franck-Condon broadening of the transition energy. For H_2O^+ , two major peaks are observed at BE 12.6 and 14.8 eV, which correspond to the literature values for vertical ionization of the $1b_1$ and $3a_1$ orbitals, respectively, of the water monomer [40]. A minor contribution from ionization of the $1b_2$ orbital is identified at BE ~ 18.6 eV.

For $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$, the measured BE spectrum shows a single peak structure centered at BE 11.5 eV which is lower than the vertical ionization potential of the $1b_1$ orbital (12.6 eV) in the water monomer. As can be seen from the sketched minimum energy geometry of the dimer in the inset of Fig. 3(b), it is formed by a hydrogen bond including the hydrogen atom of one molecule (the H donor) and the oxygen atom of the second molecule (the H acceptor) [39,41–43]. Due to the different roles of the two water molecules in the dimer, their valence orbital energies are different, with the calculated $1b_1$ binding energies being 11.92 eV for the H donor and 13.45 eV for the H acceptor [41]. The measured BE spectrum indicates that the stable $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ ion is formed by removing an electron from the $1b_1$ orbital of the H-donor molecule.

FIG. 4. Kinetic energy distributions for H_3O^+ , $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{H}^+$, $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_4\text{H}^+$, and $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{H}^+$. The spectra are normalized to unity at the peak maximum and they are offset by 0.2 for better visibility.

where $\text{H}\cdots\text{OH}$ represents the H-donor molecule. Subsequently, there is fast proton transfer.

This reaction was discussed in previous studies [14,39,44], which show that the cation equilibrium geometry is strongly different from the neutral dimer geometry and, thus, it is far from the Franck-Condon (FC) region of the neutral dimer. Therefore, in a vertical transition a vibrationally excited, and in most cases a dissociating, state is reached [14] where the OH radical is emitted. Stable dimer ions are only formed for FC transitions reaching the ionic potential energy surface (PES) below the dissociation energy. The fact that Fig. 3(a) contains no higher-lying lines shows that for ionization of other orbitals the parent ion is unstable and dissociates.

It is generally accepted that no stable nonprotonated $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n^+$ ($n > 2$) species are produced via Franck-Condon transitions starting from the equilibrium neutral cluster geometry [19]. The stable cluster ions $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n^+$ exist but, like for the dimer discussed above, their geometrical structure is rather different from the neutral cluster. In a vertical transition only points on the ions' multidimensional potential energy surfaces can be reached, which are above the barrier for proton-transfer. Therefore, at least one OH group is emitted even for ionization of the outermost $1b_1$ orbital. If there is more excess energy available, additional neutral water molecules are evaporated, leading to smaller cluster ions and with higher kinetic energies. The increase of the residual ion velocity as a function of the number of evaporated water molecules was observed before in size-selected protonated water clusters [45]. For the protonated water cluster ions, KE distributions are presented in Fig. 4. For the ions H_3O^+ , $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{H}^+$, $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_4\text{H}^+$, and $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{H}^+$ the averaged KEs amount to 83, 69, 53, and 44 meV, respectively. The KE distributions show a similar shape, with peaks at low energy. Additionally, there are tails reaching to higher energies which gradually diminish in intensity and range as the cluster size increases, while the one for H_3O^+ is particularly strong. The larger averaged KE values for the cluster ions with smaller size point to the emission of more neutral molecules. As we

will discuss below, the H_3O^+ ion is the endpoint for all larger cluster ions with sufficient internal energy to evaporate all the water molecules.

From the above averaged KEs one can deduce the total kinetic energy release (KER) in the dissociation, if one assumes a two-body decay:

This reaction occurs for all observed protonated ions. We obtain KER values of 176 meV (H_3O^+), 219 meV ($[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{H}^+$), 280 meV ($[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_4\text{H}^+$), and 280 meV ($[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{H}^+$). As discussed above, the assumption of a two-body decay is certainly not justified for the smaller cluster ions. On the other hand, for the larger ions the high energy tails in the KE distributions, which presumably result from molecule evaporation, are very weak. Furthermore, we find that these ions were produced with lower electronic excitation energy (see below). Finally, their KER values seem to converge to a common value of 280 meV. These are signatures that these ions are produced mainly by the reaction described in Eq. (3) with a fixed KER of 280 meV and without significant further molecule evaporation.

In Figs. 5(a)–5(d), the BE spectra are presented which were measured in coincidence with the protonated cluster ions. For comparison, the spectrum for ionization of H_2O monomers irrespective of the subsequent fragmentation (summed over all fragmentation channels) is included in Fig. 5(f). Three major BE peaks are observed for formation of the protonated water clusters, which can be attributed to the ionization of the $1b_1$, $3a_1$, and $1b_2$ type orbitals. The energy splitting of the valence orbitals mentioned above for dimers is reduced for the larger clusters $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ with $n > 2$ since the individual molecules can be geometrically arranged such that each one plays the role of H-donor and H-acceptor at the same time [41].

The BE spectra for the protonated ions in Figs. 5(a)–5(d) are very similar and can be understood as consisting of the same lines, except that for H_3O^+ the relative intensities of the peaks at BE = 15 and 18.2 eV are higher than the peak at BE = 12.5 eV, whereas for the larger cluster ions these lines are significantly reduced in intensity. The BE of H_3O^+ is not consistent with the calculated BE spectra of water dimers for H donor (11.90 and 14.21 eV) and H acceptor (13.25 and 15.77 eV) [41,42] and also our measured ionization spectrum for H donor (11.5 eV) in Fig. 3(b). These observations show that at least a large part of the H_3O^+ ions are formed from the ionization of larger water clusters $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ ($n \geq 3$) and subsequent fragmentation, i.e., in addition to OH, also neutral water molecules are emitted. A small intensity reduction of the first ionization band in Fig. 5(d) results from dimers which form the stable $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^+$ ion after $1b_1$ ionization (see discussion above). However, given the very small relative intensity of these ions in the TOF spectrum in Fig. 1, this should be a minimal contribution. The interpretation of the BE spectra is in agreement with our above discussion on the KER values and is supported by the line intensities and positions. In larger systems electronic excitation energy can quickly be transformed into vibrational energy by internal conversion. This can lead to the emission of several water molecules until the stable H_3O^+ ion is reached, as described by the process in

FIG. 5. (a–d) BE spectra for production of the protonated cations H_3O^+ , $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{H}^+$, $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_4\text{H}^+$, and $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{H}^+$, as labeled in the panels. Here, the insets show the minimal energy structures of the corresponding clusters [46]. The oxygen atoms of the H-acceptor molecule are marked in dark red to distinguish them from the H donor. (e) The sum spectrum for the ions shown in (a)–(d). Here also, an approximated contribution from the nondetected $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_3\text{H}^+$ ion was included (see text); (f) experimental BE spectra for water monomers summed over all fragment ion channels.

Eq. (4) for the proton transfer channel.

Here, the ionization of water cluster $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ triggers a fast proton transfer process in the ionized water cluster $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_n^+$, which dissociates into a protonated cluster like H_3O^+ ion, a neutral OH radical, and several H_2O molecules. The number of evaporated H_2O scales with the internal energy available. Therefore, for the larger cluster ions the line intensities decrease for increasing binding energy. The cluster ion disintegrates completely for the ionization of the more deeply bound $2a_1$ type orbital and the satellite states for simultaneous

ionization and excitation. As a result, a broad BE band from 27 to 45 eV is observed only in coincidence with H_3O^+ . This band is completely absent for the larger cluster ions, where for inner valence ionization there is sufficient energy available to evaporate all water molecules such that only H_3O^+ is produced.

The mechanism for the evaporation of neutrals can be internal conversion (IC) of the electronic energy of excited ionic states into vibration energy heating up the cluster ion. For the water monomer, Suarés *et al.* [47] have demonstrated IC by performing calculations for wave packet propagation on the multidimensional PES of the $\tilde{\text{B}} \ ^2\text{B}_2$ state $[(1b_2)^{-1}$ vacancy]. They have shown that the lower $\tilde{\text{A}}$ state is populated via a conical intersection of the PES of the $\tilde{\text{B}}$ and $\tilde{\text{A}}$ states. As result, the $\tilde{\text{A}}$ state is vibrationally excited and it can dissociate in $\text{H}^+ + \text{OH}$. It can also propagate further to the ionic ground-state $\tilde{\text{X}}$ via Renner-Teller coupling and dissociate into $\text{OH}^+ + \text{H}$. In this way the initial electronic excitation energy is converted into vibrations, eventually leading to dissociation. According to the simulations, dissociation is negligible up to 50 fs after ionization and the asymptotic branching ratios of the fragmentation channels are reached only after 10 ps. If this dynamics evolves in a cluster, the asymptotic fragmentation limits will not be reached since there is sufficient time available to redistribute the vibrational energy within the cluster and for evaporating neutral water molecules. This is in agreement with the above discussions of the KE spectra (Fig. 4) and the BE spectra (Fig. 5). Excited cluster ions produced by inner-valence ionization will relax by emission of neutrals and result predominantly in H_3O^+ , for which the corresponding peaks of the inner-valence vacancies are intense, as in Fig. 5(d).

In addition, the BE spectra in Fig. 5 show that the first BE peak ($1b_1$) shifts in going from $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{H}^+$ to $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{H}^+$ toward lower energy from 12.3 to 11.8 eV. This feature is consistent with the results in photoionization of water clusters by the AE experiments [17] and *ab initio* calculations [7]. There is a continuous reduction of the binding energy of the valence orbital in going from small to large clusters and finally to liquid water, where the work function is 9.9 eV. The reasons for this are twofold. Firstly, there is the delocalization of the electrons charge among neighboring water molecules. This concerns in particular the charge of a positive ion which becomes distributed. Secondly, in the bulk the water environment which consists from polar molecules can be considered as a dielectric medium which is polarized in the vicinity of a positive charge. As calculations show, both effects give rise to a reduction of the ionization energy [7].

Finally, we present in Fig. 5(e) the sum of the BE spectra in Figs. 5(a)–5(d). In order to account for the spectrum of the nondetected $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_3\text{H}^+$ ion we have approximated its contribution by averaging the spectra of the neighboring ions $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_2\text{H}^+$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_4\text{H}^+$. If protonated ions are the dominant residual ions after ionization, the sum spectrum corresponds to the BE spectrum for ionization of small water clusters. This spectrum, within the present energy resolution, shows a rather close resemblance with the monomer spectrum in Fig. 5(f) but with slightly lower relative intensity of the first BE line ($1b_1$). This can be due to the missing contributions of protonated cluster ions beyond $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_5\text{H}^+$, which would add mainly to the first ionization band. Additionally, as expected, there are

small shifts of the peak positions and widths compared to the water monomer.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We have performed a kinematically complete ($e, 2e + \text{ion}$) experiment for small water clusters. For the protonated cluster ions $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]_n\text{H}^+$ with $n = 1, 2, 4,$ and 5 , all charged final state particles, i.e., two electrons and one ion, were detected in coincidence and their energies were obtained. The fragmentation channels were analyzed concerning ionic masses, ionized orbital binding energies up to 45 eV, and ion kinetic energies.

A stable water dimer ion was observed. It was identified as the product of ionization of the outermost $1b_1$ orbital in the hydrogen-donor molecule of the neutral dimer, which is consistent with the previous photoionization experiments [12,14,44]. The dimer ion with the $1b_1$ hole can be stable in case it has low excess energy such that it cannot overcome the reaction barrier for OH emission.

The data from protonated cluster ions were consistent with proton transfer reactions. For ionization of the inner orbitals $3a_1$ and $1b_2$, additional neutral water evaporation was identified by the relative intensities of the BE peaks for the different cluster ion sizes. Finally, for ionization of the inner-valence orbital $2a_1$, all neutral water molecules are lost and solely the H_3O^+ ion is observed.

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